

Community Plantations with Chir Pine (*Pinus roxburghii*, Sarg.) in Eastern Bhutan: The Role of Community Preferences, Site Condition and Site Location Factors.

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Abstract

This article is based on a research conducted in Bhutan in 2002 for fulfilment of Master Degree requirements. Due to time constraints the result has not been published before. In the light of the developments that are taking place in the Community Forestry sector in Bhutan, publication of the results to reach a wider readership is considered beneficial for future developments.

Community plantations have been established in various locations of Eastern Bhutan in response to increasing forest degradation and forest product shortage. Chir pine (*Pinus roxburghii*) is the most widely used reforestation species in these plantations. This not only reflects the natural vegetation in the areas where these sites are located, but also the soil condition and site location factors and the preference of the local people.

Chir pine forest is the dominant vegetation type on the steep, dry slopes in the V-shaped valleys of Eastern Bhutan. The characteristics of the species contribute to this dominant presence. Site conditions combined with the location of the sites, greatly influence the ability of the local community to prevent cattle grazing and forest fires, two of the main detrimental factors for site success. The most pressing needs of local people pertain to timber, fuel wood, fodder and shingles. Except fodder, chir pine plantations are able to provide these products within a relatively short span of time. Therefore, chir pine is recommended as the main species for plantation on degraded sites in Eastern Bhutan.

1. Introduction

Eastern Bhutan consists of the six districts of Pema Gatshel, Samdrup Jongkhar, Mongar, Lhuentse, Trashigang and Trashigang Yangtse. The average population density is 35 people per square kilometre, but population density per square kilometre of arable land can be as high as 290 in Mongar (Dick and Yonzon 1996). The majority of the population consists of sedentary agro-pastoralists who conduct farming mainly on rain-fed dryland with some shifting cultivation and irrigated wetland. Cattle are grazed in Government Reserved Forest (GRF) on communal grazing lands in summer and in fallow agricultural fields and nearby forests at lower altitudes in winter. Although forest cover is currently estimated at 68%, with a population growth of 2.7% per annum the human and an increasing cattle population the availability of natural resources is rapidly declining. Around many villages, forests have gradually disappeared

leading to immediate firewood and timber shortages.

Past government-initiated community woodlot initiatives in Bhutan often failed due to lack of interest by the local people stemming from different perceptions and objectives on forest management (Wangchuk 1995). In response to these developments, and in line with the national policies of more community-based forest management, the Royal Government of Bhutan in collaboration with the World Bank-funded Third Forestry Development Project (TFDP) initiated a more participatory Social Forestry program. Two types of community-based forest management have been implemented, namely Community Forests (CF) and Community Plantations (CP). The main difference between the two is that CP is mainly on degraded and barren sites, whereas CF includes a substantial part of natural forest (up to 50%). During the TFDP mid-term review it was decided to increase focus on CP sites due to the slow

development of CF sites (Keil et al. 1998; Evans et al. 1996). CPs aim at participatory afforestation and reforestation as well as stemming and preventing soil erosion.

External monitoring and evaluation of the CFs and CPs were not strongly institutionalised. As a result, problems and failures as well as their origins have at times gone unnoticed. For a proper functioning of these projects, it is of importance to know what are the factors that contribute to failure and success. One of these factors is the extent to which the local objectives and external

(project and government) objectives converge and to what extent local objectives regarding forest functions and forest management responsibilities are being met in order to keep the community interested and involved in their plantation (see also Wiersum 1999; Rao 1992; MacCall Skutsch 1983).

Although this was the starting point, the research unveiled a number of other factors, which were found to be even more important determinants of failure and success (viz. Figure 1).

Figure 1 Factors contributing to success and failure of sites

2. Research Methods and Materials

The results reported here were obtained as part of an evaluation of social forestry in Eastern Bhutan focussing on the convergence of objectives between external actors and the local community (Bodt 2002). Four sites were selected in four districts of Eastern Bhutan with chir pine forest: Dozam CF in Drametse, Mongar district, Tshokpektang CP in Tangmachhu, Lhuentse district, Tshurgangpek CP in Manam, Trashi Yangtse district and Yezorongpek CP in Pam, Trashigang district (Figure 2). The selection criteria were that the date of inception of the site should be in or before 2000, and that the site should be located on Government Reserve Forest to keep the legal tenure of the sites comparable. Moreover the sites were all in areas with similar soil and climatic conditions and resulting natural vegetation consisting of mainly chir pine.

However several reasons have led to the exclusion of Dozam CF in the current discussion for comparative reasons. First of all it is formally a community forest although it has the nature of a community plantation with an almost degraded natural resource base. Secondly, its size of 300 ha (of which 100 under cultivation and settlement) is much larger than the other three sites. Similarly, the

106 households that are a member are much more than in the other sites. As a consequence, the possible uses of the site, the set of management practices and the rules and regulations governing the site are far more extensive. This might also have affected the objectives of the local people and the factors contributing to failure and success.

The fieldwork was conducted during the months of February, March and April 2002. All the sites were visited after obtaining baseline information from relevant documents and discussions with national, district and local forestry (extension) staff as well as with the TFDP staff. At the sites itself, use was made of semi-structured key informant, individual and group interviews. The basis for these interviews was formed by a general set of issues of importance to be addressed. This general set was retrieved from baseline literature and earlier conducted interviews. Key informants in this case were local community leaders and executive management committee members. Informal, open-ended group discussions were conducted with representatives of those households that were member of the management groups. For quality assurance of the retrieved information, triangulation of the results took place in individual interviews. Direct observation at the sites was also used.

Figure 2 Location of the study sites and extent of chir pine forests in Bhutan (Ministry of Agriculture 1995b)

2.1 Chir pine forest in Bhutan

Chir pine (*Pinus roxburghii*, Sarg., also called Himalayan long needle pine) is the dominant species in the Himalayan subtropical pine forests, stretching throughout the 3,000 kilometres of the Himalayan range, from Pakistan, Jammu and Kashmir, Himachal Pradesh and Uttaranchal states of India onwards into the western sub-tropical belt of Nepal (with relatively poor representation in Central and Eastern Nepal and the Indian state of Sikkim), Bhutan and some parts of the Indian state of Arunachal Pradesh. It covers an estimated 76,200 km² (Wikramanayake et al. 2001). Chir pine is considered a precious resource in the high Himalayas due to its high regeneration potential (Kumar & Bhatt 1990 in Sharma and Baduni 2000), capacity to colonise degraded habitats (Joshi 1990 in Sharma and Baduni 2000), rapid growth and high productivity (Bargali and Bargali 2000), straight cylindrical bole and high volume returns (Singh 1979 in Sharma and Baduni, 2000) and ability to yield a considerable amount of resin (Deshmukh 1966 in Sharma

and Baduni, 2000). In Pakistan, India and Nepal human intervention, mainly overgrazing, road construction, overexploitation for fuelwood and fodder, shifting cultivation and quarrying has resulted in significant reductions, up to 50% of the total area. The few larger blocks of remaining habitat are now found in Bhutan (Wikramanayake et. al. 2001). The total area under chir pine forest in Bhutan is approximately 100,891 hectares or 1,009 km² (Land Use Planning Project 1997) out of a total surface area of 46,500 km² (2.58%) and a forest cover of 26,338 km² (4.56%). Chir pine forest in Bhutan can be found in the Puna Tsang Chu valley in Western Bhutan (Punakha, Wangdue Phodrang, Dagana and Tsirang districts) and the Mangde Chu valley in Central Bhutan (Trongsa and Zhemgang districts). But the majority of these forests are located in Eastern Bhutan, namely the Kuri Chu valley (Lhuentse and Mongar districts) and the Kulong Chu- Drangme Chu valleys (Trashigang, Trashigang and Pema Gatsel districts), viz. Table 1 and Figure 2.

Table 1 Chir pine forest distribution in Bhutan¹ (Land Use Planning Project 1997)

	District	Total area (ha)	Forested area (% total area)	Forested area (ha)	Chir pine forest (% total area)	Chir pine forest (ha)
West	Thimphu	193,470	56.0	108,398	0.8	1,591
	Punakha	97,427	89.4	87,112	8.9	8,679
	Wangdue Phodrang	403,816	73.8	298,072	5.5	22,049
Central	Tsirang	63,881	76.2	48,658	4.9	3,130
	Dagana	138,868	82.2	114,108	2.0	2,745
	Trongsa	180,690	66.7	158,249	1.3	2,281
	Zhemgang	212,591	83.3	184,431	2.7	5,658
East	Lhuentse	288,758	75.3	217,350	3.0	8,687
	Mongar	194,735	88.5	172,258	15.5	30,192
	Trashigang	228,266	79.0	180,272	4.7	10,622
	Trashigang	143,812	76.6	110,095	2.1	3,029
	Pemagatshel	51,768	53.6	27,750	3.8	1,945
	Samdrup Jongkhar	230,835	77.3	178,362	0.1	283
	Total Bhutan	4,007,700	72.5	2,905,583	2.5	100,891

Eastern Bhutan is the easternmost border of large areas of chir pine forests. They form the

monospecific vegetation in the deep, dry and V-shaped inner valleys of Eastern Bhutan at

¹ Those districts, in which no chir pine forest occurs, have been omitted from this overview (i.e. Paro, Ha, Chukha, Samtse and Gasa in Western Bhutan and Bumthang and Sarpang in Central Bhutan)

altitudes from 900 to 1,800 meters above sea level (Messerschmidt et al., 2000). The valleys are affected less by the annual Southwest monsoon (June-September). The South-facing slopes of these valleys are in the rain-shadow and facing the wind. Hence they are generally drier and warmer than slopes with other aspects. This also shows in lower soil moisture and water holding capacity. The slopes have as parent material intimately mixed and metamorphosed igneous and sedimentary rocks, including phyllite, gneiss and quartzite (FSD 1997). Soil conditions are often poor, with shallow sandy loam entisols with high gravel and rock content predominant. Soil colour ranges from red to brown, with medium to coarse textures. Organic carbon is low due to low rate of organic accumulation as a result of repeated forest fires and higher water runoff on steep slopes (Rawat et al. 1999). Moreover the soils are acidic nature in nature, decreasing decomposition of organic matter. The resistance of pine needle litter and its allelopathic components also result in lower populations of bacteria, and other decomposing organisms (Usman et al. 2000). As a result of this combination of adverse conditions the biodiversity in the chir pine forests is rather low with limited species richness and endemism (Wikramanayake et al. 2001). Chir pine is considered an early successional, low nutrient demanding and shade intolerant species, which makes it the dominant species on these sites.

2.2 Use of chir pine forests

Despite the poor climatic and soil conditions and consequent low species diversity in the chir pine forests of Bhutan, they still provide the sedentary agro-pastoralists of the areas with a remarkable range of products. Of course there are the general environmental functions that forests provide, such as soil conservation, water catchment and habitat for wildlife species (most characteristically barking deer, *Muntiacus muntjak*; serow, *Capricornis sumatraensis*; goral, *Naemorhedus goral*; Assamese macaque, *Macaca assamensis*; and yellow-throated marten, *Martes flavigula*), some of which are

(illegally) hunted for meat and hides. More important however are the various timber- and non-timber forest products derived from the chir pine and other tree, shrub and understory species.

First of all, chir pine itself is in many areas where it is found the preferred timber species, which can be attributed to its long, clean and straight bole, the easy workability and the resistance against insect attack due to the presence of resin. Although *Quercus spp.* are preferred for firewood, lops and tops as well as dry branches of chir pine are used for firewood as well, mainly before the winter season. Furthermore, resin tapping from chir pine is one of the most important economic activities in Eastern Bhutan, with the resin and its distillation products turpentine oil (14%) and rosin (78%) being exported to India. Tapping is leased to a private corporation in several parts of the country (Moktan 1994). Labour shortage is the biggest constraint to this corporation. Additionally, about 44% of the population in Eastern Bhutan is engaged in resin tapping and distillation during the agricultural off-season. Tree tapping methods were unsustainable in the past but rules have been revised and control has increased to prevent trees from dying as a result of bad tapping practices. The seeds of chir pine are edible but they are used at the local level only (FAO 1995; 1996). They are however collected and sold to government nurseries to raise seedlings. Chir pine is unpalatable to any livestock including cattle. Chir pine leaf litter (needles) however is collected in autumn and used as animal bedding in stables for the cattle remaining in the stable during winter months (milking cows, calves). The next spring these needles mixed with manure are spread on the agricultural fields for fertilisation of the soil. Chir pine needles are not only collected from natural forests – the practice of sokshing or leaf litter forest is widespread in various parts of the country. Sokshing is government reserve forest that has been legally registered to a private rights-holder from which fodder and leaf litter of mostly *Pinus* or *Quercus spp.* is collected (Messerschmidt et al. 2000).

Although chir pine is unpalatable to cattle, unlike broad-leaved species such as oak, the various grasses and forbs that grow as understorey vegetation provide an important source of additional fodder. Cattle are kept by practically all households for draught power, manure, animal products (milk, cheese, butter, meat, hide, skin), status symbol and insurance in times of difficulty. Agricultural residues can only provide about 20% of the total animal fodder requirement and especially in the Eastern districts where the cattle population is large the pressure on the forests is very high (Wee et al. 1991). Herders drive the cattle into the forests to forage whatever is available and thus much of the forest, government reserved as well as communal, is used as grazing land. Overgrazing is becoming a major problem in several areas as a result of increasing cattle population and replacement of local cattle by improved, high fodder demanding Jersey breeds. During winter, when fodder in the forests of the colder highlands becomes scarce, cattle are moved down to warmer areas in the valleys (FAO 1995; 1996). Thus chir pine forest areas are under higher grazing pressure during winter season. Kotru (2000) and Gupta et al. (2000) report similar forest grazing from the Himachal Pradesh Siwaliks, and Singh (1996) described this from the chir pine forests in the Middle Hills of Nepal.

East Indian lemon grass (*Cymbopogon flexuosus* [Nees ex. Steud.] Wats.) is the most important essential oil-bearing plant with odoriferous substances. Lemon grass is co-specific in many areas with chir pine, especially on sandy or gravelly, sloping areas. Total area under lemon grass covers 34,589 hectares (346 km²) in Mongar, Lhuentse and Trashigang districts. Its major constituent is citral that is used in perfume, soap, cosmetics, pharmaceutical preparations and in the manufacturing of synthetic Vitamin A. Its collection and extraction has enormous potential as a source of employment and income through export for villagers. It provides income to around 400 families in the eastern region, and has become a more important source of income than farming

(FAO 1995). Harvesting takes place after the monsoon season with highest biomass and oil yields in September (Dhungel 1993).

Rhus spp., a typical understorey shrub in chir pine forests, provide wax (*R. verniciflua* and *R. syccedanea*) and vegetable dye (*R. similata*). Butter tree (*Aesandra butyracea* Roxb.), is used for edible oil production. This light-demanding species grows on slope in typical association with chir pine. The oil is locally used for butterlamps and in religious images (torma). The toxic residue is used for fishing (FAO 1996). Indian gooseberry or amla (*Phyllanthus emblica* syn. *Emblica officinalis* Linn.) fruits are collected for local consumption and occasionally commercial marketing as well as natural dye extraction. The fruits are especially appreciated as thirst quenchers in the hot and dry climate and as source of Vitamin C. This tree is also typically found in chir pine forests. Use of these species is however declining as cheaper, easier to obtain alternatives have become available.

It is thus clear that despite the initial appearance as a diversity-poor ecosystem with little use, chir pine forests produce a wide variety of products that contribute to self-sufficiency as well as act as income sources for rural households.

2.3 Site characteristics and utilisation

The three sites visited and described here had similar characteristics and utilisation patterns before the start of the community plantations. The site conditions were generally poor and forest stocks severely degraded, and use was limited to grazing and some collection of non-timber forest products. However, a number of differences were noted as well that turned out to be important determinants of success.

Tshokpektang CP is the only site with a moderate slope and moreover the soil is considered poor, but not rocky. However the site had become severely degraded due to the close proximity to the village. After the strict forest protection rules initiated in 1969 some

natural regeneration took place, but overall the site remained poorly stocked and was used exclusively for cattle grazing, collection of grasses for bedding, lopping of the sparse chir pines and coppicing of *Lyonia ovalifolia* (Forestry Services Division 1997).

Tshurgangpek CP is located on a severely degraded, steep slope with as only vegetation some *Phyllanthus emblica* trees, lemon grass, various shrubs such as *Butea buteiformis* (Voight), forbs and grasses. The site was exclusively used for free range grazing, as there was grass available closer to the village for usage as bedding and fodder (Forestry Services Division 1998).

Yezorongpek CP is the most recently established of the three sites. The only vegetation consisted of *Phyllanthus emblica*, *Rhus paniculata*, lemon grass and some other shrubs and leguminous and herbaceous species. Use of the site was limited to grazing and collection of the fruits of *Phyllanthus emblica* for household use (Forestry Services Division 1999).

As can be seen from the table, the sites had been completely replanted with various tree species that were chosen by the local community on suggestion of the forest extension agents. The species were selected on basis of the benefits they were expected to provide.

Table 2 Site characteristic summary

Site characteristic	Tshokpektang CP	Tshurgangpek CP	Yezorongpek CP
Co-ordinates	91°11'34" E/ 27°36'32" N	91°38'55" E/ 27°29'11" N	91°32'48" E/ 27°18'12" N
District	Lhuentse	Trashigang	Trashigang
Block	Menbi	Toetsho	Samkhar
Village	Tangmachhu	Manam	Pam
Year of establishment	1999	1999	2000
Size (ha)	3.24	5.30	9.32
Number of households	19	27	47
Aspect	S	SE	SW
Average slope	15°	70°	60°
Altitude (approx.)	1600	1100	1200
Area planted (ha)	3.24	5.30	9.32
Species planted	<i>Pinus roxburghii</i> , <i>Eucalyptus spp.</i> , <i>Melia azaderach</i> , <i>Cupressus spp.</i>	<i>Pinus roxburghii</i> , <i>Persea fructifera</i> , <i>Eucalyptus spp.</i> , <i>Juglans regia</i> , <i>Schima wallichii</i> , <i>Cupressus spp.</i> , <i>Cryptomeria japonica</i>	<i>Pinus roxburghii</i> , <i>Eucalyptus spp.</i> , <i>Juglans regia</i> , <i>Tectona grandis</i> , <i>Cupressus spp.</i> , <i>Dendrocalamus spp.</i>
Land tenure	GRF	GRF	GRF

3. RESULTS

3.1 External and local objectives for plantation establishment

The objectives of the national social forestry policy and the TFDP regarding the CPs are a combination of those for community forestry and afforestation and reforestation projects. In this, the role of the TFDP has been purely advisory and facilitating towards attaining government's objectives. These objectives have been identified as (Forestry Services Department 1996; Maier 1996; Wee et al. 1991; Messerschmidt et al. 2000):

- The involvement of local people on the rehabilitation in of degraded forest areas and their subsequent management and increase their technical, institutional and organisational skills and capacities.
- The integration of trees into farming systems and thus improving the viability of the local economy
- To assist forest users in developing forest based home and cottage industries

As can be seen in Table 3 the main objectives of the local community were related to production functions of the forest and mirror the most urgent needs of local population: timber, fuel wood and fodder. Even though kerosene and gas cylinders have now found their way to Pam and Tangmachhu, firewood is still the main source of fuel in all three areas and is used for cooking and heating. Firewood has to be collected on a regular basis and therefore the availability of

firewood in close proximity to the village is an objective shared by all. The first position in Tshurgangpek CP is however occupied by timber instead of firewood. This can be explained by the fact that firewood is still available at relatively close distance from the villages whereas timber has to be brought from Bhutanese territory at the opposite side of the river. This entails floating the logs in the river and transporting them through Indian territory, which takes one to two days and moreover the villagers face a lot of harassment at the Indian side of the border. Fodder is an important objective in the two sites that do not have adequate grazing land for cattle nearby. Yezorongpek CP has grazing land at a ridge above the village. Shingles for roofing are being increasingly replaced by corrugated iron sheets. The members of Tshurgangpek CP are relatively less affluent and live at greater distance from the road. The replacement of traditional wooden shingles by iron sheets is slower, therefore the demand for shingles is still high here. Aesthetic considerations and soil erosion prevention were mentioned in Yezorongpek CP only, which is explicable by its location close to the village, agricultural plots and the national highway.

Table 3 Objective priorities in the four sites

Forest product/function	Tshokpektang CP	Tshurgangpek CP	Yezorongpek CP
Fuel/firewood	(1)	(2)	(1)
Timber	(2)	(1)	(2)
Fodder	(3)	(4)	-
Shingles	-	(3)	-
Landslide control	-	-	(3)
Site improvement	-	-	(4)

Although an exact one-to-one convergence of external and local objectives could not be observed, they were clearly interrelated in all cases. The objectives of both government and local people flow from their problem perceptions, and when these converge, the actions they take will be the result of more successful cooperation and thus contribute to

success. In the preparation of the management plans a participatory approach was taken and as such the objectives of the local community have been properly included in the plans. The extension agents had a crucial role in forging this convergence between local communities and external objectives. However, as mentioned earlier, in the research it was found

that there are other factors that also contribute to success or failure of the sites as well.

3.2 Factors affecting success and failure of sites

The results of the CPs have been mixed. Tshokpektang CP is a great success. The whole area has been replanted, grazing and forest fire have been effectively prevented and controlled, and there is a high level of co-operation and satisfaction among the community members. The only noted problem was the low survival rate for species other than chir pine, which resulted in planting of chir pine seedlings only.

Yezorongpek CP was another success story with high community participation, the total area planted, and effective grazing and forest fire prevention. The same problem concerning

seedling survival was observed here too. Unfortunately, a wild fire incidentally caused in April 2002 resulted in the whole plantation being destructed. However the community members were still willing to continue with the plantation and rededicated their commitment. Tshurgangpek CP had met the same fate earlier on when a wild fire lit by hunters from across the border burnt out of control and the whole plantation was destroyed. The assistance provided after this event, from both government and project side, was minimal and the community members lost their interest in continuing with the CP. A complicating factor was the inability to prevent cattle grazing as a result of which they refused to replant the area unless wire fencing would be provided.

Figure 3 Tshokpektang CP in Tangmachhu village, Menbi block, Lhuentse district. The left (north) face of the slope is privately registered and well-stocked sokshing, whereas the right (south) face of the slope is the 4-year old community plantation with chir pine. Notice the gentle angle of the slope and rather thick herbal cover.

A number of factors were reported and observed to be influencing the success and failure of sites (viz. Figure 1). Community homogeneity and co-operation were found to be good among all villages. The dedication of the local forestry (extension) staff and the TFDP staff was high to very high in two out of three sites. This pertained to their personal

involvement, but also advice and assistance in technical aspects of plantation and institutional capacity building among household members. Only in Tshurgangpek CP the extension services provided were very poor or even absent, one of the reasons for loss of interest and general dissatisfaction among the members. The perceived need for forest products was high in all the sites,

although in Tshurgangpek CP this need was most pressing. The presence or absence of short-term benefits (inherent to the nature of a plantation) was not considered a major factor of failure. In all cases the local communities had a medium to long-term view on benefits such as timber, and were satisfied with smaller benefits such as fuel wood through lopping and coppicing on the short term. The

threat of outside extraction was of moderate importance in only one site. Strict regulation and enforcement of the regulation by the households was generally seen as sufficient to prevent outside extraction. Only in Tshurgangpek CP the threat pertained to cattle from other villages, and hunters from across the border with India.

Table 4 Factors contributing to failure and success

Factor of failure/success	Tshokpektang CP	Tshurgangpek CP	Yezorongpek CP
Community homogeneity and co-operation	Very high	Moderately high	High
Site accessibility and visibility regarding			
- overall	High	Poor	Very high
- fire control	High	Poor	High
- grazing control	High	Poor	Very high
Site/soil conditions	Moderately poor	Very poor	Poor
Site size	Very small	Small	Small
Dedication local forestry (extension) staff	High	Very low	Very high
Perceived need	High	Very high	High
First accumulation of benefits	Medium to long term	Long term	Medium to long term
Outside threat	Absent	Moderate	Absent

Based on these results and the discussions with the community members, dedication of forestry (extension) staff, site accessibility and visibility and site conditions were considered to be most important determinants of the result of the community plantations. The first factor was an exception in the case of Tshurgangpek CP, since overall dedication of forestry extension staff was found to be high. A probable reason for the lack of assistance provided there, as expressed by the local people, might be the relative remoteness

3.3 Site and soil condition factors

The overall condition in all the sites is moderately poor to very poor. This refers to both the soil conditions as well as the climatic conditions. The soils are shallow, rocky, nutrient-poor and acidic in nature. The slope aspect makes the sites dry due to less precipitation in combination with long hours of sunshine and wind. These conditions make the sites unsuitable for many tree and shrub species, which is reflected in the sparse

of the site, at five hours from the nearest road head and seven hours from the district headquarters. The latter three factors directly or indirectly determine the ability of the community to prevent forest fires and cattle browsing destroying the plantation and thus the choice of three species and will now be discussed in more detail. All these factors are also presented in Figure 3. What becomes clear is, that in all these sites chir pine is the preferred species for plantation.

vegetation consisting of only a limited number of tree (mainly *Aesandrea butyracea*), shrub, grass and forb species. Chir pine is most probably the natural (climax) vegetation on these slopes.

This has direct impact on the species that can be used for replanting on the sites. Based upon the wishes of the local people for timber, fuel wood, fodder, and to a lesser shingles, the government and project extension staff suggested a number of species for planting (viz. Table 2). Soon however it

became clear that most of these species were ill suited for the sites, a fact earlier mentioned by the community plantation members but not taken into account. In fact, of all species planted only chir pine has grown well in the

sites, and seedlings of all other species have not survived long. This resulted in the practice of people to plant only chir pine in plantation sites, and use other species for agroforestry purposes. They also realised that areas with chir pine, after the trees have reached above browsing height, can provide grazing ground for cattle, whereas mixed plantations with palatable tree species would have to be kept grazing-free for much longer periods. At the same time they stated that chir pine is able to provide for timber and fuel wood and can thus fulfil their most pressing needs. They preferred to plant fodder tree species on the homesteads to facilitate prevention of cattle browsing. Moreover chir pine is a fast growing species that can provide them with products within a relatively short time period. Therefore they did not see

limiting species choice to chir pine as a major problem.

3.4 Site size and location factors

Site location factors pertain to accessibility of the site, visibility of the site from the village, and size of the site. These factors are of primary importance in relation to the ability of the household members to prevent, detect and act against forest fire and browsing of cattle in the plantation site, the main causes of plantation failure. Both the cattle population as well as the occurrence of forest fires makes the amount of effort the community members have to put into protection measures extremely high. Social constraints can also make this difficult. Site location factors are a main determinant in the extent to which the community can control illegal grazing of cattle, and destruction of planted forest by forest fire. Therefore both issues will be treated here separately.

Figure 4 Tshurgangpek CP, Manam village, Toetsho block, Trashy Yangtse district. The site is located on a very steep and inaccessible slope with rocky soil and sparse vegetation. Several shrubs and trees previously affected by fire are visible too.

3.4.1 Cattle grazing; prevention, detection, and punitive measures

Free grazing of cattle is one of the major uses of forests in Eastern Bhutan. This poses serious threats to the success of community plantations, since the cattle can destroy tree

saplings either by direct browsing or by trampling of non-palatable species such as chir pine. As such all the management plans have specific rules prohibiting the grazing of cattle for some years until the saplings are above browsing height, which in practice is between five to eight years. This grazing ban can be implemented in various ways, such as barbed wire fencing (nailing barbed wire to poles or live trees all along the plantation), live fencing (establishing a boundary of unpalatable live plant material thick enough to prevent cattle from passing through) and social fencing (a common understanding among local people to control animal access without physical restraint). In absence of government and project funding, the first option has been considered too expensive in all of the community plantation sites, and the second option is not feasible due to the size of the sites and the site conditions. Therefore, social fencing arrangements have been made in all community plantations. Cattle herders are urged to restrain their cattle from entering the plantation area. Member and non-member households whose cattle is detected inside the plantation face fines ranging from Nu. 25/- per head of cattle plus Nu. 50/- per destroyed sapling and replanting of destructed area, to confiscation of cattle for repeat offenders (Forestry Services Division 1997; 1998; 1999).

The success of the social fencing system has been mixed and depends on the number of cattle traditionally using the area, the availability of alternative grazing land as well as the location from the site vis-à-vis the village. In Tshokpektang and Yezorongpek CPs the social fencing practice has been successful. The number of cattle is limited, and alternative grazing land is available in nearby forests. Additionally, the sites are in the immediate vicinity and visibility from the village. This enables the watchmen and the household members to keep a constant vigil and take immediate action in case cattle are seen entering the plantation area. The importance of these factors is reaffirmed by the experience in Tshurgangpek CP. Here the social fencing is not successful and cattle have been a constant threat to the plantation.

The site is located on a steep slope below the village, and thus out of sight. Another problem is that the number of cattle traditionally using the low-elevation site as winter grazing ground is very large (several hundred heads) and good alternative grazing ground is not available. A final complicating factor is that people from adjoining villages also graze their cattle in the area, and repeated warning and fining led to deteriorating social relations. In order to prevent further conflict, the members decided to stop the social fencing mechanism. Without commitment from the government side to provide barbed wire and poles they have expressed unwillingness to continue with the plantation.

3.4.2 Forest fire prevention, detection and combat

Forest fires are an integral part of the chir pine forest ecology throughout the Himalayas due to the climatic and vegetative conditions (Semwhal and Mehta 1996). Chir pine has a certain tolerance for fire after it reaches a certain height and even after losing all its needles as a result of fire it will vigorously rejuvenate the next season. The accompanying ground vegetation such as lemon grass and other leguminous species are tolerant to and dependent on fire as well. However, to small chir pine seedlings and saplings forest fire can be as destructive as to any other species.

Therefore the community plantation management plans duly recognise the risk that forest fires pose to the plantation areas. Apart from the nation-wide Forest and Nature Conservation Rules of 1995 and 2000, which state the responsibilities of citizens to prevent and combat forest fires as well as fines for offenders, the management plans include additional rules. In all the plans there are provisions for the cutting of a fire line (ranging from four to ten meters) around the plantation to stop fire from spreading onto the site. Watchmen are appointed from the members on a rotational basis and against cash or in-kind compensation. They have the duty to keep a constant eye on the plantation and adjoining areas. The management plans

also mention the fines that will be imposed in case of accidental or deliberate causing of a fire which damages the plantation. Although the Community Forestry Rules leave the option open to management groups to design their own rules, in this case all the groups decided to refer to the Forest and Nature Conservation Act of 1995 and Rules of 2000 (Ministry of Agriculture 1995a and 2000). Fines generally range from replanting of the destructed area to Nu. 5,000/- per hectare. In case of actual fire threatening the plantation, all the member households are responsible to assist in fire suppression and prevent the fire from spreading into the plantation. There are fines for absentees.

Despite these arrangements, protecting the sites against destruction by fire has proven to be very difficult. In Tshokpektang CP the members have managed to prevent forest fires from damaging the site on various occasions.

The location of the site on a gentle, less dry slope, in combination with the clear visibility from the village has contributed to this. In Tshurgangpek CP, a forest fire below the site caused by hunters from across the border in the late afternoon was transported upwards very fast by the hot, dry afternoon winds. By the time the fire was detected, a consequence of the location out of sight of the village, it was dark and the fire could not be extinguished. After this event no punitive action could be taken against the culprits since they were non-Bhutanese nationals and no such arrangements exist. At the same time the assistance provided by the project and government for replanting the area has been absent. As a result the community members have lost interest in the plantation. In 2004, after discussion with the villagers, the CPMG was dissolved.

Figure 5 Yezorongpek CP, Pam village, Samkhar block, Trashigang district. The location of the site near the village and national highway is clearly visible. This picture was taken several days after the destruction by fire.

In Yezorongpek CP, a fire was accidentally started by a youth from another village walking along the footpath crossing the plantation, who threw away a cigarette bud without properly extinguishing it. Despite the fact that the fire was detected rather quickly due to the close proximity to the village, again

a combination of strong winds and dry highly combustible material as well as the source of the fire right in the middle of the plantation made it impossible for the community to extinguish the fire. This site has been partly replanted with completion in the current season expected, and punitive action against the culprit has been taken. Thus it can be said

that rather than community commitment, which was high in all sites, site location and condition factors are far more instrumental in determining the success of fire prevention, detection and combat.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

4.1 Chir pine ecology, forest transformation and species choice

Chir pine as a pioneer species on degraded, marginally fertile and xeric sites seems the appropriate choice. Rawat and Pant (1999) and Zomer et al. (1999) concluded this as well. However the question remains how the forest will or should preferably develop in the long term. Under no disturbance from outside, the normal successional pattern would be that under increased soil nutrient availability and higher light interception due to increased foliage, shade-tolerant *Quercus spp.* would replace chir pine stands (Bargali and Bargali 2000). But chir pine could be considered the climax vegetation on south-, southwest- and southeast-oriented slope aspects in Eastern Bhutan, which is in line with similar findings from the Garwhal Himalaya in India (Dhanai et al. 2000; Sharma and Baduni 2000). The dominant vegetation on slope aspects other than the southerly oriented ones consists of temperate evergreen forests of oaks (mainly *Quercus lanata*, Smith and *Q. griffithii*, Hook et Thom.). It has been observed in other parts of the Himalayas (i.e. Garwhal: Semwhal and

Mehta 1996, Bhandari et al. 2000, Semwhal et al. 1999; Kumaun: Dogra 1999; Bargali 1997; Bisht 1990; Singh and Bisht 1992) that when due to various anthropogenic factors the microclimatic conditions change (increased light and nutrient availability), pioneer species such as chir pine invade the late successional and climax forest. *Quercus spp.* are generally in higher demand for fuel wood, fodder and timber than chir pine. But they are far less tolerant to dry, acidic soils and other adverse conditions. The growth of *Quercus spp.* can be suppressed by chir pine due to the higher nutrient utilisation efficiency of chir pine, especially towards lower nutrient and moisture levels (Bargali and Bargali 2000). *Quercus spp.* are also far more susceptible to cattle browsing. Additionally, the chir pine dominated valleys have a long winter and early spring dry season when burning is frequent. Experience from India shows, that frequent uncontrolled fires have detrimental impact on the forests, helping in the expansion of pine forests at the cost of ecologically important and socially valued oak species (Semwal 2002). Thus it seems unlikely that in the long-term chir pine plantations can, naturally or human-assisted, develop into mixed coniferous-broadleaved forests. Taking into account the needs of the local communities, this is neither required nor feasible. Moreover, the occurrence of forest fire and dependence of cattle on the forest for grazing make chir pine the preferred species.

Figure 6: Factors resulting in choice of chir pine for community plantations

4.2 Forest fire

In pine forests world-wide, fires are not an unnatural factor entirely created by man, but they have always been a constantly occurring phenomenon (Agee 1998). Pine trees have a thick bark and high resprouting capability. Bark thickness may be the single attribute that best characterises a species adaptation to fire (Martin 1989). The ability to continually resprout following top killing enables a species to survive (Van Lear 1991). As such pines are considered fire adapted ecosystems because their continued existence depends on the periodic occurrence of fire (Agee 1998). The impact of fire on any ecosystem depends on factors such as origin of the fire, type of fire, topography of the landscape, structure of the vegetation, types of fuel and fuel loading, season of burning and post fire precipitation (Semwal 2002). Forest fires are influenced by the weather variables and the accumulation of fuel on the forest floor. Weather variables include low water content and high surrounding temperature increasing the inflammability of igniting material. Regarding fuel for the fire, same authors found that chir pine forests have less leaf mass on the forest floor, but a high partially decomposed mass compared to *Quercus spp.*

In Bhutan, as in Nepal and India, there are various causes of fires in the chir pine forests. Chhetri (1994) reports that 40% of the forest fires are caused by out-of-control debris burning on agricultural fields (for soil preparation at the end of the winter months), 30% from intentional burning for new grass for cattle, 25% by uncontrolled camp/cooking fire and fires lit for road maintenance, and 5% by smokers. This brings the total human-induced forest fires on 100%. Surface fire is the most common type of fire in chir pine forests, with occasional crown fires. Surface fire follows two main modes of spreading. It may travel down from hilltop to hill base generally at a slower pace, or may ascend up from base to top. The ascending flame spreads at high speed and is very difficult to control (Semwal 2002). It may thus turn into crown fire and incinerate large areas of forest.

Chir pine trees of shoulder height and above are fairly resistant to burning (Sharma and Baduni 2000). It is mainly the other tree, undergrowth shrub, leguminous and herbaceous species and accumulated pine needles that are highly inflammable. This is especially true of the predominant undergrowth species with chir pine, lemon grass which has high oil content. Burning of

the herbage cover consisting of lemon grass has been an important management tool for local farmers. The increased nutrient availability and decreased competition by other species results in new grass shoots that on the one hand serves as food for cattle and on the other result in higher yields of lemon grass oil. After a forest fire, favourable growth conditions occurs including high temperature, bright but often cloudy conditions, high solar irradiance (due to reduced canopy) and high humidity due to major precipitation events (monsoon), which influence recovery of seedlings and saplings. Burning is also a management tool applied by farmers to reduce pest incidence in agricultural fields and cattle.

Forest fires remain the single most serious threat to plantations in Eastern Bhutan. An average of 50 forest fires occurs in Bhutan per year. Eastern Bhutan falls within the high fire risk zone, with a precipitation of less than 1,000 mm annually, high day-time temperatures and afternoon winds. The forest fire season runs from January to June with as peak month March (Chhetri 1994). During these dry and cold winter months the perennial grasses become drier, a process accelerated by the fierce winds. This causes fires to spread fast. Once alight it is extremely difficult to extinguish a fire due to the location of the sites with poor accessibility and adverse climatic conditions facilitating fast spread of the fire. Therefore there is a greater need for prevention and timely detection of fires. Considering that most fires have an anthropogenic source, awareness campaigns should continue to educate local people about causes and consequences of forest fires. Location of new plantations on sites more visible from the village is another way to facilitate detection of fires.

4.3 Cattle grazing

After forest fires the second most important threat to plantations stems from browsing by cattle. The social fencing system enforced in the first few years after plantation can only be successful when sites are relatively small and well in sight of the village, when the number

of cattle is low, when cattle grazing in the area is owned by the same people as those who manage the plantation and when there is alternative grazing land available at not too much distance from the village. If such is not the case, no matter how high community co-operation is, the social fencing will fail. Experience from the Middle Hills of Nepal shows that the physical success of chir pine community plantations can be largely attributed to annihilation of seedling loss by grazing as a result of the unpalatability of chir pine for cattle. At the same time the experience there learns that the social success of the plantations is less apparent. Grazing bans interfere with the traditional grazing patterns and practices and decreases fodder supplies thus lowering cattle productivity and household income. This leads to dissatisfaction among local people (Singh 1996), and social fencing rules will no longer be adhered to. In those cases it could be considered to provide alternative fencing, such as for example barbed wire fencing. Although this entails a rather high investment, in many cases the local people greatly value it and are willing to invest financial and labour resources to construct it. In Tshurgangpek CP, it is even a prerequisite for people to continue with, or rather restart, the plantation.

Considering the importance of cattle for the livelihoods of local people, assuring continued and stable supply of grazing land (both on forest and pasture lands) is of great importance. Pasture rehabilitation efforts within a community plantation (Dozam CF in Drametse, Mongar) have been unsuccessful. Grass yields in sites which have been afforested have shown to increase considerably, but the imposition of a grazing ban has as side effects that nutrient input from manure cease which in combination with increased removal of grass biomass result in a worsening of the nutrient status of the soil (Kotru 2000). The long-term productivity of combined grass production and tree plantation can therefore not be maintained with a grazing ban in place, which is another argument for temporary bans and favours the unpalatable chir pine over other species. A

major disadvantage is, that herbage production under chir pine is reportedly low due to high solar radiation interception (Anderson et al. 1969 in Gupta et al. 2000), low leaf-litter decomposition due to lower ground level temperature (Bhandari et al. 2000) and release of allelochemicals from the pine needles (Modgil and Kapil 1990 in Gupta et al. 2000). However, herbage density was found to be highest under trees followed by saplings and poles due to differences in solar flux interception, and this solar flux interception was found to be more important than the amount of litter fall (Gupta et al. 2000). Thus herbage productivity in maturing chir pine plantations would increase as a result of decreased radiation interception in combination with increased nutrient availability due to lifting of the grazing ban. However Singh (1996) reports different findings from the Middle Hills of Nepal. There, the closed canopy of mature chir pine plantations reduced undergrowth and thus forage supply. Here however the seedlings had been very densely spaced at the time of planting to expected seedling mortality. In the CPs of Bhutan, a more wide spacing had been used, leaving enough space for solar radiation to reach the ground. This way, the combination with a grazing ban would increase herbage cover and after a few years grazing in the plantation area could resume.

4.4 Future development of Community Plantations

The Community Forestry sector in Bhutan is currently undergoing rapid developments. At the time of this research there were only a few forests under community management, most of which like the sites described here were plantations. However recent changes in attitude of the Department of Forestry towards Community Forestry have created a climate in which the government is planning to hand over an estimated 10% of all Government Reserved Forest to local communities for management. This means communities will have increased management responsibility, not only for plantations but also for natural forest.

Tshering (2003) in his research found that when forest resources are more degraded the forest as a source of products was considered most important, whereas when the forest are largely intact the protection for the children was the main objective. This confirms the results found in this study, in which the sites are degraded and increasing the availability of forest products is the main objective. Unfortunately, most CP sites in Eastern Bhutan are too small to provide the local community with all the forest products desired on the short term. Certainly in the early years after plantation and to a lesser extent in the later years they remain dependent on Government Reserved Forest. The extension of CPs into CFs, which include natural forest, should therefore be encouraged in order to keep local people interested and motivated.

Also, the site location and condition factors should be more taken into account for CP and CF establishment. In many of the degraded sites in Eastern Bhutan that qualify for reforestation the species choice is limited by the climatic and soil conditions. At the same time the location should be on gentle and easily accessible slopes, located within sight of hamlets. This will facilitate detection of forest fire and illegal browsing of cattle. Tshering (2003) also reported that local people have a lot of knowledge concerning the choice of species, including the preference and performance under local conditions.

In India, small scale, community-managed broad leaf forests are increasingly replacing government-initiated, large-scale commercial chir pine plantations. Local communities in the Garwhal and Kumaun Himalayas have continuously put in more effort to extinguish fires in oak forests compared to chir pine forests. Reasons for this are the more difficult control of fire in chir pine forests, less value of chir pine forests compared to multi-purpose mixed oak-rhododendron forests, decreasing groundwater levels in pine forests and reduced undergrowth due to allelopathic properties of the needles (Dogra 1999). The chir pine plantations did not meet their objectives and thus their interest was absent.

However, the small-scale community plantations in Bhutan are of a completely different nature.

Chir pine seems the most suitable species for reforestation in sites such as Yezorongpek, Tshurgangpek and Tshokpektang Community Plantations in Eastern Bhutan. Not only do the site conditions favour this species over others, but they are also most suitable in light of the particular problems of grazing and forest fire. At the same time, they alleviate the local communities of their most pressing needs for fuel wood and timber even within a relatively short time span. But despite this community plantations are no panacea for the problems of local people. Community-based management of more extensive natural forest resources is necessary to improve living conditions in the rural areas of Eastern Bhutan in the long term as well. Community plantations however are a great opportunity for local people to improve their capacity in natural resource management.

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